

“TO STAND WITH PALESTINE IS TO BE HUMAN”: A LITERARY ANALYSIS OF THUNBERG’S ANTI-COLONIAL ADVOCACY THROUGH FANONIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

This article delves into the humanitarian vocal solidarity shown by globally celebrated environmental activist Greta Thunberg to the Palestinian cause, placing Thunberg’s narrative in a broader literary postcolonial framework. While many question her dedication to human rights labeling it as a popularity stunt, this research perceives Greta’s anti-settler speeches not as a political deception but as a strong voice of resistance against human rights violation. Fanon’s idea of resistance and decolonization has been used in the research to examine the significance of resilient struggle in order to reclaim freedom and human dignity, as shown by Thunberg. The research is based on the Qualitative research method and Thunberg’s social media posts, protest speeches and international media interviews have been used to scrutinize how her narrative closely relates to Fanonian rhetoric. The study aims to describe the importance of strong resistant voices like Greta Thunberg, keeping in view the dehumanization era, humans are witnessing in today’s world. By conducting research on Palestinian resistance and interconnecting it with strong anti-colonial voice of Thunberg, this research contributes to the Palestinian decolonial struggles, calling for the entire human race to stand in solidarity with Palestinian oppressed people against the brutal Israeli occupation, because nobody is free until Palestine is free.

INTRODUCTION

Greta Thunberg is a globally recognized Swedish climate activist who gained popularity across the world due to her unapologetic and bold statements which directly challenges the authorities and governments who in her opinion are responsible for the environmental crisis. Although this young girl is only 22 years old, her resistance against the established corrupted system has made her a global sensation. The world was okay when she used her voice to challenge

those who destroy the ecosystem but her voice suddenly became unbearable to many when she started to challenge those who deliberately destroy human lives. In October 2023, Greta Thunberg showed her solidarity with Palestinians by sharing a post where she and three other girls were holding signs on which were written statements like: "Free Palestine," and “Stand with Gaza”, supporting those who have been the victim of Israeli cruel occupation

for decades. Her support for Palestine became a heated debate on social media and while many agreed with her stance against Israeli oppressors, many started to give hateful comments and the most important point is that this hate came mainly from those in power like German politicians and international media.

This pro-Palestinian post shared by Greta made people believe that she is using the climate movement to show her support for Palestinians, ignoring the fact that saving the humans is as much significant as saving the planet. Many German politicians and people globally called her antisemitic and even the Israeli government shared their disapproval against her statement but no threat and warning was able to deter the resolve of this young activist who decided to stand for this Earth since the age of 15. Her statement that she posed on X stated clearly that: "Today we strike in solidarity with Palestine and Gaza. The world needs to speak up and call for an immediate ceasefire, justice and freedom for Palestinians and all civilians affected." (Thunberg, 2023) This resistance by young Greta bothered the Israelis so much that the Israeli military spokesperson said: "Whoever identifies with Greta in any way in the future, in my view, is a terror supporter," also saying that "Thunberg is sweeping the terror of the Palestinians or Hamas and Islamic Jihad under the table as if it did not exist." (Shalika, 2023) These statements of Israeli authorities and international media are just an attempt to cover their own heinous crimes that they are committing against humanity, crying out shamelessly that they are the victims and anyone who dares to support the true oppressed would be labeled as Jihadi, Terrorist and Antisemitic because the fact is that the colonial powers also control international media and those sitting on mighty positions.

Israel occupied Palestine in 1967 and their violence against Palestinians traced back to 1960s not since 2023 as they claim in the media in order to justify that they became inhumane instantly after Hamas attacked them and they have the right to commit as many human crimes as they want because they were also attacked. The United Nations (UN) recognizes that Israel is practicing an extreme form of apartheid in Palestine and the actions of the Israeli army are a total violation of universal human rights. The secretary general of Amnesty International and Human Rights

Watch, Agnes Callamard showed anger against the Israeli government's actions stating that: "Whether they live in Gaza, East Jerusalem and the rest of the West Bank, or Israel itself, Palestinians are treated as an inferior racial group and systematically deprived of their rights." (Callamard, 2022)

Israeli people are illegal settlers who are taking over Palestinian's land by displacing and killing them. As of today 2025, Israeli government and forces are killing hundreds of Palestinian civilians on a daily basis, most of whom are innocent children and women. The Israeli forces are blocking any humanitarian food aid to enter Gaza, causing people of Palestine to die out of starvation. Gaza now has the largest population of child amputees in the world because Israeli forces bomb schools and houses which fell on the innocent children's bodies but according to Israeli's mighty opinion, nobody should even speak against these animal-like activities because it would be labeled as antisemitism. Tom Fletcher, who is an Under-Secretary-General for Humanitarian Affairs and Emergency Relief Coordinator said in his briefing to UN on May 13, 2025 that: "Israel is deliberately and unashamedly imposing inhumane conditions on civilians in the Occupied Palestinian Territory, nothing has entered Gaza for more than 10 weeks, hundreds of thousands of Palestinians have been forcibly displaced and 2.1 million Palestinians in the Strip face the risk of famine. Few hospitals that have somehow survived bombardment are overwhelmed" He also stated that: "I can tell you, from having visited what's left of Gaza's medical system, that death on this scale has a sound and a smell that does not leave you." (Fletcher, 2025)

This research argues that Greta's support for Palestine is not a deviation from the climate safety movement. The protection of the planet lies in the safety of human basic rights which would make this planet worth-living. Fanon's work on colonization is largely expressed in his note-worthy works including *The Wretched of the Earth* and *Black Skin, White Masks*, where he argues that colonization is not only a political occupation but it also includes the projection of dehumanization where colonizers are perceived as civilized and colonized people are meant to be portrayed as savages. He also argues that violent and strong resistance is vital to liberate one's homeland from colonization because silence cannot be an

option as he said: "For the colonized, to be a moralist is to silence the arrogance of the colonizer, to break up his brutal display of violence in short, to show him that he is no longer king of the castle". (Fanon, 1963) This study aims to explore the stance of Greta Thunberg through Fanonian perspective in order to understand the power of linguistic resistance as Fairclough said that language is not merely discourse but it has the power to enforce or even challenge the power structures. (Fairclough, 1995)

1.1 Research Objectives

1. To analyze Thunberg's support for Palestine through Fanonian idea of decolonization
2. To explore the importance of global resistance during anti-colonial struggles in the context of Palestine
3. To examine the situation of colonized Palestine by employing Fanon's ideas

1.2 Research Questions

1. How does Greta Thunberg's support for Palestine align with the Fanonian idea of decolonization?
2. What kind of significant role can global resistance against Israeli genocide play in the context of Palestine?

1.3 Research Significance

This research holds immense significance as it raises a voice of resistance against Israeli oppression and genocidal action that are ongoing in Palestine right now. It urges that showing resistance against Israeli cruelty on educational, economical, moral and vocal platforms is a vital duty of every conscious human so that this planet can become worth-living. By giving acknowledgement to Greta Thunberg, this study asserts that any act of resistance against the oppressor shown by anybody should be appreciated and the world needs more voices like this young climate activist in the current situation. By explaining the situation of Palestine through Fanon's lens, this research contributes to the ongoing debates on justice and freedom for Palestine and its people, emphasizing that literature has a significant role to play when humanity is in severe crisis. It also urges that youth activism and strong voices of anti-colonial discourse has the capability to challenge oppression and systematic colonial power structure.

1.4 Delimitation

This study will only focus on Greta Thunberg's statements of solidarity for Palestine, excluding many other globally recognized activists sharing the same stance. Only those statements of Thunberg about Palestine will be analyzed which she stated after October 2023. The theoretical approach will also be limited to one main theory, the theory of Decolonization and resistance given by Frantz Fanon in his noteworthy postcolonial works..

2. Literature Review

Bleibleh (2013) in his doctoral dissertation *Everyday Life: Spatial Oppression and Resilience under the Israeli Occupation. The Case of the Old Town of Nablus, Palestine* explains the sufferings and traumatic challenges that Palestinians went through because of Israeli military invasion in an old town named Nablus. Israelis controlled both people and the place of Palestinian land by using violent powers and inhumane practices which brought a man-made destruction in Palestine. Psychological burden, Fears and traumatic feelings of Palestinians have been portrayed in this research, employing theories given by noteworthy thinkers which includes Lefebvre, Paulo Coelho and Michel de Certeau. Interviews of victims were also taken to convey the real pain and perspective of oppressed Palestinians. The study also asserts that Palestinians still hold a strong sense of identity and resilience despite going through the worst colonial occupation which demonstrates the power that resistance and resilience holds.

Malhotra & El-Shaarawi (2025) in their work *We want to live as other children live': Palestinian children's resistance to genocide as 'fighting for life* argues that just like Feminism is a great motive of the world which will lead the society to welfare and progress, standing against genocide is as much important as standing against women oppression. Those Feminists who want equal rights for every human should raise their voices of resistance against cruel Israeli occupation of Palestine. They need to stand against the genocide that Israeli government and Army is carrying out in Gaza. The study states that Palestinian children are experiencing the worst crimes against humanity happening in front of their eyes, they lose their relatives, parents and siblings, sometimes they become victims of bombing

themselves, losing their healthy perfect body but they are still surviving. They are not experiencing beautiful childhood as they are supposed to be like every other child of the world, they are surviving genocide yet they are not passive victims. They are face of strong resistance, resilience and bravery. Their resistance reflects a powerful form of decolonial struggle which Fanon talks about in his Postcolonial works.

Hekala (2025) in his work *The Settler-Colonialism Framework in the Israel-Palestine Conflict* discusses the difference between colonialism and Settler Colonialism. Researcher argues that during colonialism, foreign powers try to get commercial, economic and political control of the colony to gain power but in case of Settler Colonialism, the aim of colonial powers is to take over the colonized permanently by removing the native population using force. This type of settler colonization is far more brutal and aggressive than the simple colonization although the effects of both are disastrous. Settlers try to take superior position in someone else's land by portraying the native indigenous people as barbaric, uncivilized and inferior. This dehumanization of native colonized people enables the settlers to commit genocide easily as the world doesn't care. This systematic control over an entire population and their land forces the victims into a state of "otherness", presenting them as people who don't deserve equal rights and whose lives are less worthy than other human beings.

Jamshidi (2024) in her work *Genocide and Resistance in Palestine under Law's Shadow* explores the double double standard of international laws and international courts when it comes to the genocide happening in Palestine right now. There is a close relation of genocide, power and international standards of justice. The study examines South Africa's case filed against Israel's inhumane practices going on in Gaza, scrutinizing the hypocrisy of the International Court of Justice. While Israel is continuously violating the international humanitarian laws and every law of the United Nations charter, the powerful international institutions who are supposed to empower and protect humanity are in deep sleep. These institutions label Palestinian resistance as violence and Israeli brutal occupation as the fight for survival. The research emphasizes that Palestinians have every right

to show resistance against cruel inhumane Israeli practices, forcing the illegal colonial power to evacuate the land they have stolen shamelessly.

Seidel et.al (2024) in book *Resisting domination in Palestine: Mechanisms and Techniques of Control, Coloniality and Settler Colonialism* explains the multiple economic, political, intellectual and environmental rooted colonial strategies that Israel uses in order to maintain its control over Palestine. Writers offer a deep exploration of how these very systems of control used by Israeli settlers become spaces for Palestinian resistance. In this settler-colonial hegemony, colonial powers control education, government, health institutes and economic systems to exploit the colonized people. The book provides a detailed examination of the ways which the settler and colonial Israeli regime uses to acquire a sustainable and systematic control of Palestinian land and its people.

Bazian (2024) in his research article *Introduction: Fanon's Palestine and the Colonial Dividing Line* employs Fanonian perspective about colonialism on Israel-Palestine ongoing situation and emphasizes that the ideas given by Fanon in the context of colonization and decolonization fits perfectly in Israel-Palestine conflict. Researcher explains the ways colonizers make the colonized feel dehumanized and unprivileged by making separate colonies, checkpoints and militarized zones. This way, colonizers make the impression on colonized that they are in every domain superior, dominant and more privileged than them, emphasizing that colonized people are inferior than settler ones. This stark division and brutal contrast between settlers and colonized is also seen in the difference of their homes, buildings and life-styles. While Palestinians live in constant fear of bombing, Israelis enjoy the luxuries of life, eating and living on stolen land shamelessly. Children of Palestine die from starvation and lack of medical facilities but the settler ones get to enjoy each and every happiness of life. This is a structured and systematic plan of colonizers to decrease the self-determination and self-pride of colonized people according to the Fanonian narrative. Bazian also discusses the enduring ability and persistence of Palestinians who are showing resistance to brutal colonization and still fighting for their freedom.

Kai (2025) in his book *Don't Look Away: The Children Are Dying and the World Is Watching: Gaza's Genocide, Denial, and Empire's Moral Decay* talks about drastic situation of Gaza. Although the main focus of research is not Greta's solidarity with Palestinians but she appreciates the bravery and courage of Greta Thunberg in the context of Palestine. Kai demonstrates that Greta didn't choose to remain silent for the sake of comfort. She gave her stance in solidarity with Palestine and its people stating that: "Even in a world of cowardice, the courageous will not be silenced." She saw a great deal of criticism from Israeli people and the genocide supporters all across the world who tried to defame her by giving her the title of "Little Jihadi" but Thunberg's stance about Palestine didn't change. She also tried to deliver food aid to Gaza where Israel is still imposing a man-made famine catastrophe, giving a strong message to the world that resistance is never weak and common people have the capability to change world's brutal order and they must play their role in stopping a genocide.

Weinger (2024) in his article *When the World Collapses in Palestine* discusses that human rights protection and environmental safety cannot be dealt with separately. The situation in Palestine is not different from environmental catastrophe and it should be taken seriously across the world. Researcher employs the concepts of great philosophers including Mahmud Darwish and Edward Said to challenge the anti-Palestine narrative that Israel is spreading throughout the world portraying that Palestinian lives are not worthy like other human beings. The land of Palestine cannot be named as "zone of non-being" to normalize the inhumane actions of Israeli forces and government. The settler's attitude aligns with the anthropocentric ideas where one type of living being is considered worthy while others can be easily destroyed and killed.

Research Gap

Although a number of research articles have been written on Greta Thunberg and her advocacy for climate protection, a gap remains open as no study has been undertaken to analyze Greta's support for Palestine. This research aims to fill this gap by exploring the connection between Greta's pro-Palestine movement and the real-life disastrous

situation of Palestinians who are living under Israeli illegal brutal occupation.

3. Methodology

This study is based on a qualitative research approach, utilizing the close reading method to study and analyze Greta Thunberg's stance about Palestine. Thunberg's official statements including social media posts on X (Twitter) and Instagram since October 2023 have been studied which portrays her strong resistance against Israeli bloody occupation of Palestine. The statements given by Thunberg on international TV channels and global media will also be explored using the Fanonian perspective to explore Greta's narrative thoroughly.

3.1 Theoretical framework:

This research is based on anti-colonial ideas given by great theorist, Frantz Fanon in his works *The Wretched of the Earth*. Fanonian ideas regarding the importance of anti-colonial resistance give a strong basis to understand the Palestinian resistance and the significance of Greta Thunberg's efforts. Fanon claims in his works that colonization is not merely political control and the projection of dehumanization is always evident in colonization where the colonized people are seen as those savage, uncivilized and less-worthy people whose lives don't have much significance. Fanon says in his book *The Wretched of the Earth* that the colonial world is divided into two worlds, the first luxurious world belongs to colonizers and settlers who live in well built houses with comfort. He says:

"The settlers' town is a strongly built town, all made of stone and steel. It is a brightly lit town; the streets are covered with asphalt, and the garbage cans swallow all the leaves, unseen, unknown and hardly thought about. The settler's feet are never visible, except perhaps in the sea; but there you're never close enough to see them. His feet are protected by strong shoes although the streets of his town are clean and even, with no holes or stones. The settler's town is a well-fed town, an easygoing town; its belly is always full of good things. The settlers' town is a town of white people, of foreigners." (Fanon, 1961)

On the contrary, the colonized people live in war zones where they are never safe and well-fed just like people living in Palestine particularly in Gaza. Fanon

says their places are like a “world without spaciousness”, where people live in misery and pain. He explains the situation of colonized people in these lines: “They are born there, it matters little where or how; they die there, it matters not where, nor how. It is a world without spaciousness; men live there on top of each other, and their huts are built one on top of the other. The native town is a hungry town, starved of bread, of meat, of shoes, of coal, of light. The native town is a crouching village, a town on its knees, a town wallowing in the mire.”(Fanon, 1961) These statements given by Fanon in 1960s suits well with the Israeli-Palestine situation where Palestinians are dying of hunger in their own land while Israeli come from all over the world and live in Palestine like this land belongs to them which It certainly not! According to Fanon, to get rid of the brutal colonization, the process of decolonization is necessary and Decolonization is never a friendly or magical event, it is marked by a lot of sacrifices and struggles. He stated that:

“National liberation, national renaissance, the restoration of nationhood to the people, commonwealth: whatever may be the headings used or the new formulas introduced, decolonization is always a violent phenomenon.....Decolonization, which sets out to change the order of the world, is, obviously, a program of complete disorder. But it cannot come as a result of magical practices, nor of a natural shock, nor of a friendly understanding. Decolonization, as we know, is a historical process.” (Fanon, 1961)

The intellectuals and warriors who advocate anti-colonial rhetoric like the climate activist Greta Thunberg, have always been and will always be in a difficult spot because the governments and institutions they are standing against are controlling the worldly power. They control the media, hence they rule narratives just like they showed the world that Greta is using Palestine for publicity. Fanon says that to fight with those cunning authorities, a man and society needs to be strong, bold, steadfast, organized and violent because the opposite party contains power, status and control. Fanon explains in his book that young people of the world and particularly of the underdeveloped\colonized nations are the most important part of that nation and eventually the planet Earth, hence they should

educate themselves regarding the ongoing politics in the world so that they can understand the hidden power games ongoing in this globe.

“The young people represent one of the most important sectors. The level of consciousness of young people must be raised; they need enlightenment. To educate the masses politically does not mean, cannot mean, making a political speech. What it means is to try, relentlessly and passionately, to teach the masses that everything depends on them; that if we stagnate it is their responsibility, and that if we go forward it is due to them too, that there is no such thing as a demiurge, that there is no famous man who will take the responsibility for everything, but that the demiurge is the people themselves and the magic hands are finally only the hands of the people.” (Fanon, 1961)

The world can only see the reality when they know that what most of the media is offering them is a lie and these information systems are being used to manipulate their minds. Of course, the colonized ones know the truth as they are experiencing the brutal colonial reality themselves but the entire world need to realize that truth which is very naked now as the world is watching a live genocide happening through the social media. At this moment, silence cannot be the choice of conscious people of the world and they must show resistance like Greta Thunberg against Palestinian genocide and children mass murder which is evident and no-one can deny this cruel reality. This article will use the above discussed Fanonian ideas described in his book *The Wretched of the Earth* to explore the anti-colonial resistance shown by Greta Thunberg against the brutal Israeli government and armed forces.

4. Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Examining Dehumanization in Palestine: The Colonial context

The significance of resistance shown by Greta Thunberg can only be understood when it becomes clear that what she’s standing for is a moral and upright mission. The Palestinian freedom is not only the freedom of people belonging to Palestine but it is necessary to protect humanity because if the world allows a genocide to happen of innocent people and doesn’t take strong measures to end it, the history will remember this period as one of the darkest times in

human legacy where people chose to remain silent when it was not even an option. Palestinian land has been under the occupation of Israel since decades and Israelis have been dehumanizing the people of Palestine in every way possible. Their army bomb their houses, hospitals and schools, killing thousands of children brutally and seeing this situation, anyone who advocates for Israeli actions is just an accomplice of this genocide. Those people who speak up against the inhumane activities happening in the world need to be encouraged because they are saving the face of humanity which in current times is covered in the blood of innocent children. No one is exempted from the responsibility of Palestinian bloodshed as the situation is becoming disastrous with the passing time. Yanis Varoufakis who is a former Greek Finance minister expresses his solidarity with Palestinians, stating that:

“As I utter these words,” Varoufakis said, “Palestine, and Gaza in particular, is being bombarded to smithereens. It is not the time to study the Palestinian issue; this is the time to defend the very existence of the Palestinians. “In the West and in the world at large, we are part of a war propaganda, the purpose of which is to justify fully the state of apartheid, ethnic cleansing, and the annihilation of the people of Palestine.” (Varoufakis, 2023)

In 2023, thousands of British artists and celebrities wrote a public letter explaining the drastic situation in Gaza. They stated that: “We are witnessing a crime and a catastrophe, Israel has reduced much of Gaza to rubble, and cut off the supply of water, power, food and medicine to 2.3 million Palestinians. In the words of the UN's undersecretary for humanitarian affairs, 'the spectre of death' is hanging over the territory.” They also demanded their government to stop being a supporter of genocide and they emphasized on the need of an immediate lasting ceasefire. These kinds of voices in solidarity of Palestine are somehow a positive ray of light in the dark chapter of humanity, reflecting that there are people left in this world who speak out against injustice when silence could be more comfortable for them. The situation in Gaza and Palestine is testing the morality of governments and people all across the world and while many people are being a positive influence, there are also many ill-minded cruel people who are supporting the killing of children and civilians in Palestine. Thameen Al-

Kheetan, who is Spokesperson for the United Nations (UN) High Commissioner for Human Rights shares on 24 June, 2025 the dreadful situation in Gaza, explaining that:

“Desperate, hungry people in Gaza continue to face the inhumane choice of either starving to death or risk being killed while trying to get food....Palestinians across Gaza are suffering from hunger and the lack of other lifesaving necessities. The Gaza Strip remains on the verge of famine as a result of Israel's closure and blockade, as well as ongoing unlawful restrictions on the entry and distribution of humanitarian assistance. The weaponisation of food for civilians, in addition to restricting or preventing their access to life-sustaining services, constitutes a war crime....The Israeli military must stop shooting at people trying to get food.” (Al-Kheetan, 2025)

According to the Ministry of Health in Gaza, since October 2023 nearly 59,000 Palestinians have been killed in Gaza including 26,655 men, 9,497 women, 17,921 children, and 4,307 elderly and 139,607 people have been reported severely injured. These statistics have also been confirmed by OCHA, United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. (UNRWA, 2025) UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) gave statement on 17 July, 2025 that The UN Special Rapporteur Reem Alsalem called the sufferings of Palestinian women as Femi-genocide, reporting that Israel is intentionally killing Palestinian women and girls. According to estimates, among the 58,000 killed Palestinians in Gaza since 2023, 67 percent are women. She stated that: “What is happening to Palestinian women and girls is not collateral damage of war, It is the intentional destruction of their lives and bodies, for being Palestinian and for being women.” She also explained the psychological sufferings of Palestinians, adding that:

“The horrors that Palestinian mothers, in particular, continue to endure watching their children slowly starve, killed, maimed, and buried alive is killing them repeatedly in a single day. The psychological trauma they, and all Palestinians in Gaza, are suffering knows no boundaries. The destruction of Gaza's health infrastructure has reportedly left 150,000 pregnant and lactating women without access to essential care. An estimated 17,000 of these women and 60,000 children under five now suffer from acute

malnutrition. At least 60 children have died from starvation since March 2023, following Israel's blockade on food, medical supplies, and humanitarian aid," she said. "This is in addition to the 50,000 children who have been reported killed or injured since October 2023." (OHCHR, 2025)

According to the Committee to protect Journalists CPJ's investigations, the situation of Palestinian journalists can be categorized as the deadliest period of history because according to estimates, at least 186 journalists have been killed and 124 have reported injured in Palestine by July, 2025. Although journalists are protected by international law and killing them comes under war crimes, it seems that Israelis are able to commit the worst crimes possible and they can easily get away with it. Most of the governments, powerful authorities, international media networks and global justice courts are watching people being starved and killed without a hitch of shame and embarrassment. In this context although Israel is the main oppressor in Palestinian context but those who shake its hand soaked in the blood of thousands of Palestinian children are equally a part of oppressing force and all those who resist in any possible way they can, have become a part of Palestinian cause because saving Gaza is equivalent to saving humanity. Carlos Martinez de la Serna, who is the director of CPJ said in New York that:

"Since the war in Gaza started, journalists have been paying the highest price of their lives for their reporting. Without protection, equipment, international presence, communications, or food and water, they are still doing their crucial jobs to tell the world the truth. Every time a journalist is killed, injured, arrested, or forced to go to exile, we lose fragments of the truth. Those responsible for these casualties face dual trials: one under international law and another before history's unforgiving gaze." (CPJ, 2025)

4.2 Fanonian perspective and Greta Thunberg's unwavering support for Palestine

Fanonian perspective regarding decolonization and resistance has a deep connection with Greta Thunberg's solidarity with Palestinian cause. When talking about Palestinian sufferings was considered anti-Semitism particularly in October 2023, Greta played valiant role in calling genocide a genocide

when it could put her in a difficult spot. In October 2023, Greta shared a post on X, showing support for Palestinians. She got hate and criticism from the media, authorities and even the public from all over the world but none of it could stop this courageous and fearless girl from standing on the right side of humanity. She never considered the criticism, backlash and condemnations that were being imposed on her more significant than the people of Gaza, explaining her deeper connection with the humans living all across the world. While delivering her speech in her homeland Leipzig, Germany in 2024, Greta stated that:

"To stand with Palestine is to be human. We cannot remain silent. No one can remain silent when there's an ongoing genocide and when people are denied the most basic human needs. We must always stand up and speak up against oppression, against imperialism, against war, and against discrimination and racism in all forms. We cannot allow ourselves to be silenced." (Greta, 2024)

Fanon emphasized in his work that in order to decolonize a nation, it is necessary to reject the inferior and degraded identity imposed on colonized people by the colonizers. It is significant for the colonized people to know that they are not sub-humans and they deserve every happiness that other people in the world are enjoying. Greta Thunberg follows this Fanonian ideology when she always calls Palestinians with love, respect and warmth, like they belong to her and their lives are significant and worthy to fight for. This is what Fanon calls Re-humanization of colonized people. She faces criticism, hateful comments, mockery and even jail to raise her voice for Palestinian freedom, affirming that their rights and their lives are precious and no one has the right to steal them. People criticized her that she is a climate activist and she should be only focused on that motive but Greta believes and states to the world boldly and resiliently that saving humans is more significant than saving environment because if humans don't have basic rights than what's the point in fighting for the world which is not even worth-living. While giving interview to a journalist of Middle East Eye, Greta gave her views regarding this criticism:

"It is very absurd that in times of genocide, policymakers who are complicit in this genocide are using this opportunity to spend their energy to try to

mock people who are at least trying to do something. It's so weird to me that people are separating caring about the environment and the climate to caring about humans. I care about the environment and the climate because I care about human and planetary well-being. Those are the same thing. In my view, we are standing up for justice and for sustainability, for liberation for everyone. There can be no climate justice without social justice. We cannot pretend to care about the future of humankind and how our children will be affected in the future.” (Greta, 2025) While the sold international media was glorifying the role of Israel and showing them as the “victims”, Greta turned the table by changing the narrative game. Due to her fame and recognition across the world, she influenced the people globally who were somehow perplexed. This resonates with the ideas given by Fanon on his book *The Wretched of Earth* where he insists that changing the narrative is important for decolonization because the illegal settlers and colonizers maintains their power by manipulating and exploiting information sources, just like International media is serving the Israeli government and forces even now, when it is evident and clear that they are committing genocide. Greta uses her platform and fame for all the right reasons by being the voice of voiceless and she raised her voice instantly, not waiting for the things to come in favour as the situation was critical in October 2023 after Hamas's attack on Israel. She says in her interview to international media that: “We cannot just sit by and allow this to happen. We are watching, all of us on our phones are watching a genocide happening for decades and decades of systematic oppression, ethnic cleansing, occupation. If I for example have a platform or something, then I have to use that in times of injustice. We all have a responsibility to do something and we are trying to do that and step up when our governments are failing to step up.” (Greta, 2025) She also calls the powerful people and governments complicit in Genocide fearlessly, showing her bravery, and loyalty to nothing but humanity. During her interview with Amy Goodman, she holds the governments accountable for their silence and complicity in genocide of Palestinians. She says that: “Right now international law is failing us. International institutions, our governments are failing us. Media, our companies are all failing us. Or “failing

us” is a diplomatic way of saying that our system seems to be designed in a way that is built upon exploitation and oppression of people. And so, there's no one to turn to. There's no one we can turn to to rescue the situation, but it falls on us to step up, to continue flooding the streets, to continue organizing, boycotting, to speak up on all platforms to try to send a clear message that we will not stand for what is happening right now.” (Greta, 2025)

Fanon calls for international solidarity in his works in order to gain real liberation and Greta is doing this in practical terms in the context of Palestine. She takes action and speaks up for people who don't belong to her religion, ethnicity, colour or nation but what connects her with them is having a human heart. Her support never remained just verbal and she arranged and joined several protests, criticizing those who support the killing of people and raising voice for the oppressed people of Palestine. During a Pro-Palestine rally in Milan, she said that: “You cannot claim to fight for climate justice if you ignore the suffering of all colonized and marginalized people today. Stepping out of our comfort zones and demanding an end to this suffering is a question of basic humanity and we call on everyone to do so. Silence is complicity. You cannot be neutral in a genocide.” (Greta, 2024) She was labeled as a mad child and even supporter of terrorists but none could deter the devotion, dedication and ambition of this young activist to call a spade a spade. She remains steadfast even though powerful people are now portraying her as negative as they can. She says it very clearly:

“Even as the world tries to silence us, we will come back every time even louder because everything is at stake and none of us are free until everyone is free. No climate justice on occupied land! There is no climate justice without social justice. We cannot live on a planet where a genocide is allowed with the eyes of the world that are not doing anything about it and they are funding the war of Israel and the crimes of Israel against the Palestinian people with money that could go to the ecological transition.” (Greta, 2024)

Greta's support for Palestine is not merely vocal as she even decided to join the Freedom Flotilla mission which aims to deliver humanitarian aid to Gaza directly by breaking the siege. Regardless of all the danger associated with this mission, Greta departed on a ship with aid for Gaza with 11 other activists,

delivering a strong message to the world that everyone has a duty to act with responsibility because humanity is at stake. In her message to the world regarding this mission, she said that: “It falls on us as communities, as human rights defenders to take that responsibility to say and do what needs to be said and done. There is simply no other option to do everything you can to demand accountability. Israel is using starvation as a deliberate weapon and the Freedom Flotilla Coalition has made a promise to Palestinians that they will continue to do everything they can to break the siege of Gaza and to protest and stand in solidarity with Palestinians. And that promise is being kept.” She endangered her life, comfort and security for the people on the other side of the world who are in pain and hunger when the world chooses to remain silent. She proclaims that:

“What is happening in Gaza right now is unprecedented. We do not accept this genocide. We do not accept the illegal occupation and siege and apartheid state. How can we expect a world that lets that happen? How can we expect that world to take a few steps back to prioritize ecology or the future of our biosphere and living planet? There can be no climate justice on occupied land, no climate justice without social justice.” (Greta, 2025)

Although, she didn't succeed in breaking the aid blockage but she was able to send a strong message to the people living on planet that they must do everything in their capability and power to stop this genocide. At this critical time of history where starved people are being killed while trying to get food, hospitals are being bombed and children are being murdered brutally, no one has the option to remain silent. She was kidnapped from ship sailing to Gaza and was deported to Paris in June, 2025 where she said while talking to media at Paris' Charles de Gaulle Airport that: “On international waters, we were illegally attacked and kidnapped by Israel and taken against our will to Israel where we were detained. And then some of us were deported, some are still there. There are very big uncertainties because it was quite hell again and uncertain.”(Greta, 2025) Fanon's ideas and Greta's statements go hand in hand and Greta's resistance against apartheid, inequality, colonization and genocide holds immense significant in today's immobile world where people seek comfort rather than purpose. This resistance needs to come from the

entire world, from every beating heart and from every person who calls him\herself a human because this is the only way to save humanity. As Greta said:

“We cannot afford to give up. There is simply too much at stake. And in times of injustice, as we are seeing now, the genocide and blockade happening, we have to do everything we can to demand an end to these atrocities and war crimes committed by Israel. And if my presence on this boat can make a difference, if that can show in any way that the world has not forgotten about Palestine, and to try once again to attempt to break the siege and open up a humanitarian corridor and deliver the extremely needed humanitarian aid, then that is a risk I am willing to take. And it's something that we just simply have to do. We cannot just sit around and do nothing and watch this live streamed genocide unfold in front of our very eyes. So we are doing this because we are human beings who care about justice.” (Greta, 2025)

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has clarified through credible statistics, evidence-based information and reliable sources that what's happening in Palestine and particularly Gaza is clearly a genocide and Greta Thunberg is playing a heroic role by showing solidarity with Palestinian people. Her actions and statements regarding Palestine are not some publicity stunt or political deviation but they show her commitment towards the welfare of human beings living on Earth. Those who criticize and mock her due to her stance regarding Palestine are just trying to lessen the positive influence of Greta on other young activists across the world as this will be challenging for the illegal settlers and baby-killers. By observing Greta's resistance in the broader landscape of Fanonian ideology, this research has deeply explored the importance of resistance when human lives and basic rights are on stake.

Recommendations

This research only focuses on the resistance shown by Swedish climate activist Greta Thunberg, further research can be conducted by exploring the statements of other globally recognized activists, journalists and celebrities who support Palestine and raise their voice against illegal Israeli occupation. The resistance shown by Palestinian people and particularly their

journalists can also be explored in future research papers.

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